

Effects of Molybdenum on Phosphorus Concentration in Rice (*Oryza sativa* L.)

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Abstract : A hydroponic trial was carried out to investigate the effect of molybdenum (Mo) on uptake of phosphorus (P) in different rice cultivars. The experiment was conducted using a randomized complete-block design, with a split-plot arrangement of treatments and three replications. Four rates of Mo (0, 0.01, 0.1 and 1 mg L⁻¹) and five cultivars (MR219, HASHEMI, MR232, FAJRE and MR253) provided the main and sub-plots, respectively. Interaction of molybdenum×variety was significant on shoot phosphorus uptake ($p \leq 0.01$). Highest and lowest shoot phosphorus uptake were seen in Mo3V3 (0.6% plant⁻¹) and Mo0V3 (0.14% plant⁻¹) treatments, respectively. Molybdenum did not have a significant effect on root phosphorus content. According to results, application of molybdenum has a synergistic effect on uptake of phosphorus by rice plants.

Keywords : molybdenum, phosphorus, uptake, rice,

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